

Application of the MAX Algorithm for Secure Autonomous Cryptographic Key Generation in the Internet of Things (IoT)

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Abstract:

The aim of this paper is to apply the MAX (Mathematical Applied to eXryption) algorithm to the Internet of Things (IoT) to ensure secure and autonomous cryptographic key generation.

The proposed system reduces vulnerabilities associated with key transmission, thereby enhancing the security of IoT devices.

MAX is particularly suitable for environments characterized by devices with limited computational power, due to its adaptability and scalability.

This proposal addresses the critical security needs for the widespread adoption of IoT.

This work builds upon previous publications on Zenodo:

- **Function for Prime Numbers:** describes the mathematical function underlying MAX:
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12658465>.
- **MAX (Mathematical Applied to eXryption):** describes the functioning of the MAX algorithm:
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14066752>.

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) represents a rapidly expanding technological paradigm, characterized by the interconnection of heterogeneous devices capable of autonomously collecting, exchanging, and processing data. These devices, often limited in terms of computational power and energy resources, are used in numerous contexts, including smart homes, industry, healthcare, and connected vehicles. The widespread adoption of IoT introduces new security challenges, particularly concerning cryptographic key management and communication protection.

Secure management of cryptographic keys is one of the most critical aspects to ensure the integrity and confidentiality of data transmitted between IoT devices. Traditional key management approaches, which often involve key exchange over potentially vulnerable networks, are not always suitable for IoT devices that operate in resource-constrained environments and may be subject to various types of attacks, including man-in-the-middle attacks and attacks from adversaries equipped with quantum technology. Moreover, the wide variety of devices and their geographical distribution complicate the implementation of centralized security solutions.

The MAX algorithm was developed to address these specific challenges. MAX is an innovative cryptographic algorithm that enables secure and autonomous key generation without the need to transmit the keys between devices. This significantly reduces vulnerabilities associated with key transmission over insecure networks, making MAX particularly well-suited for use in IoT contexts. The approach proposed by MAX is based on the generation of local, synchronized keys using shared parameters between devices, which ensures effective security even in the absence of direct connection between the devices.

In this work, I propose extending the MAX algorithm for specific application to the Internet of Things, with the goal of demonstrating that MAX not only meets the security needs of IoT but also represents a scalable and adaptable solution for devices with limited resources. Autonomous key generation, without the need for transmission, represents a significant step forward in protecting data in IoT networks, ensuring security even against advanced threats, including quantum attacks.

This work extends the previous document by focusing on the practical application of the MAX algorithm in the context of IoT, with the aim of providing a robust and effective solution for cryptographic key management in distributed and potentially vulnerable environments.

CHAPTER 2:

FEATURES OF MAX FOR IoT

MAX has been designed with specific characteristics that make it particularly suitable for application in IoT. Below are the main features that enable MAX to meet the unique requirements of IoT devices.

Adaptability

The MAX algorithm is highly adaptable to the hardware limitations typical of IoT devices, which often have constrained computational power and memory. Thanks to its efficient structure, MAX can generate cryptographic keys with minimal computational overhead, ensuring adequate performance even on resource-limited devices. This adaptability is crucial for securing devices such as sensors, actuators, and microcontrollers, which constitute a significant part of the IoT ecosystem.

Synchronization

A fundamental aspect of implementing the MAX algorithm in IoT is the initial synchronization between devices. Synchronization is achieved using predefined shared parameters, including an initial seed, an agreed number of iterations, and various other parameters for the autonomous generation of future keys. These parameters are configured during an initial setup phase. Once synchronized, devices can generate consistent cryptographic keys without requiring additional communication, thereby reducing the attack surface and enhancing the system's resilience against external threats.

Key Autonomy

Autonomy is one of the hallmark features of the MAX algorithm. IoT devices, thanks to MAX, can generate cryptographic keys independently, without the need to transmit them over potentially vulnerable networks. This approach eliminates the need for a centralized key management infrastructure and significantly reduces the risks associated with key compromise during transmission. Additionally, the ability to periodically regenerate keys independently further enhances the overall system security by limiting the impact of any temporary breaches.

Algorithm Rotation

To further enhance system security, it is possible to implement algorithm rotation for prime number generation. For instance, the system can be configured to use different algorithms based on predetermined temporal factors (such as the current time), ensuring additional variability and making it even more challenging for attackers to compromise the keys.

Resistance to Attacks

The ability of the MAX algorithm to generate cryptographic keys autonomously, without ever transmitting the keys themselves, provides significant defense against quantum attacks. Since there are no keys in transit to analyze, even an attacker with a quantum computer would lack access to the critical data needed to deduce the keys. This sets MAX apart from traditional algorithms that rely on key distribution and may be vulnerable to such attacks. This resistance is particularly relevant in an IoT context, where security must be ensured despite the presence of heterogeneous and potentially vulnerable devices.

The MAX algorithm offers a range of features that make it ideal for use in the Internet of Things. Its adaptability, initial synchronization capability without additional communication, key generation autonomy, and resistance to attacks are key elements that overcome the limitations and vulnerabilities typical of IoT devices.

CHAPTER 3: FLOWCHART OF THE MAX ALGORITHM PROCESS FOR IoT

This section describes the flowchart of the operational process of the MAX algorithm for IoT, highlighting the key stages involved in cryptographic key generation and management.

1. Generation of Initial Seed and Number of Iterations

The first phase involves generating the initial seed (Random Initial Value) and the number of iterations, which must be randomly created and transmitted shortly before synchronization. This ensures that each device has unique and fresh values to start the key generation process. This approach significantly reduces the risk of a compromised device endangering the entire system, as the initial seed is not stored long-term. The initial seed is a securely generated random value that, along with the number of iterations and predefined synchronization time, enables devices to begin the key generation process simultaneously.

2. Prime Number Generation

- The system generates a **Random Initial Value** with 100–120 digits, adjustable based on the device's computational capacity.
- A **Random Number of Iterations** between 1000 and 1500 is generated; this value can be increased depending on the device's capabilities. A higher iteration count increases the probability of finding prime numbers.
- Using these parameters, MAX generates several **Prime Numbers** with a uniform digit length (approximately four times the digits of the Initial Value) and a **Common Prefix** containing digits equal to about one-third of the Prime Numbers' length.

3. Cryptographic Key Generation

MAX uses the generated prime numbers, the number of iterations, and the common prefix to produce the cryptographic key. This feature ensures that every connected and synchronized device autonomously generates the same encryption key at the same time. To enhance security further, the key can have a limited lifespan (e.g., 10 seconds, 10 minutes, 1 hour, etc.), depending on the security requirements and computational resources.

4. Key Regeneration

At every subsequent synchronization:

- MAX uses the **common prefix** from the prime numbers of the previous session as the new **Initial Value**.
- The **New Number of Iterations** is calculated by adding or subtracting the digit count of the common prefix to the previous value, ensuring it remains within the range of 1000 to 1500. If the result falls outside this range, a correction is applied (by adding or subtracting the common prefix digit count).
- To ensure the new Initial Value maintains the required digit length (e.g., between 100 and 120), the system may append additional digits from the common prefix to meet the minimum requirement.

5. Continuous Synchronization

Using the new parameters, each synchronization cycle enables devices to autonomously generate the new cryptographic key. No encryption keys are transmitted between devices, making the system significantly more secure compared to approaches where keys are shared over a network. This process allows the system to continuously generate new keys without requiring external instructions. Device synchronization must be maintained to ensure accurate key generation for secure message encryption and decryption.

This flowchart clearly outlines the various stages of the cryptographic key management process in the MAX algorithm, demonstrating how autonomous key generation and the absence of key transmission significantly reduce system vulnerabilities.

CHAPTER 4:

USE CASES IN IoT

The MAX algorithm can be applied in various Internet of Things (IoT) contexts to enhance communication security and ensure a high level of data protection. Below are specific use cases:

1. Security in Smart Homes and Smart Cities

In smart homes, MAX can be used to enable connected devices, such as thermostats, security cameras, smart locks, and sensors, to authenticate each other without the need to exchange keys over the network. This approach significantly reduces the risk of interception and man-in-the-middle attacks, as the keys are never transmitted and are autonomously generated by the devices.

- **Smart Homes:**

MAX ensures the home environment remains secure, even when new devices are added or the home network faces risks such as Wi-Fi router vulnerabilities.

- **Smart Cities:**

The same principle applies to smart cities, where MAX can secure communications between critical infrastructures, such as traffic lights and environmental sensors, maintaining security in scenarios of greater scalability and complexity.

2. Industrial IoT (IIoT)

In industrial environments, the MAX algorithm enables secure communication between sensors and central systems, even in critical conditions.

- **Use Case Example:**

In monitoring and control systems for industrial plants, it is crucial to ensure that data collected by sensors is transmitted securely to supervisory and control systems. Using MAX, cryptographic keys are autonomously generated by each device without the need for transmission over the network. This approach reduces the attack surface and enhances system resilience to threats, ensuring high-level security even when the communication network is vulnerable or under challenging environmental conditions.

3. Connected Vehicles

In the context of connected vehicles, the MAX algorithm provides a secure method for continuously updating cryptographic keys without relying on a central network or external connections.

- **Features:**
Modern vehicles are equipped with numerous sensors and communication systems that collect and share data both internally and with external infrastructure.
- **Use of MAX:**
Vehicles can generate new encryption keys at regular intervals, ensuring that internal communications between systems (e.g., infotainment, safety sensors, engine control units) remain secure.
- **Resilience:**
Even in cases of temporary disconnection from the network, MAX allows vehicles to maintain basic security by locally regenerating keys, enhancing system robustness.

Example: Heterogeneous Security in a Smart Home with Devices of Different Computational Capacities

Scenario:

A smart home includes a variety of connected devices, such as:

1. **Central Hub** (highly capable, manages all connections)
2. **Security Camera** (high computational power)
3. **Smart Lock** (medium computational power)
4. **Temperature Sensor** (low computational power)
5. **Motion Sensor** (low computational power)

Step 1: Initial Synchronization

The central hub is responsible for initial synchronization and parameter distribution for key generation. Due to the heterogeneous nature of the system, two groups of devices are established with different parameters:

- **Primary Group:** Security camera, smart lock, and central hub.
 - Parameters:
 - **Initial Seed:** 100 digits.
 - **Iterations:** 1000–1500.
 - **Prime Numbers:** 400 digits.
- **Secondary Group:** Temperature sensor and motion sensor.
 - Parameters:
 - **Initial Seed:** 11 digits.

- **Iterations:** 500–700.
- **Prime Numbers:** 45 digits, with a 6-digit common prefix.

Step 2: Key Generation

- **Primary Group:**
Devices in this group generate cryptographic keys using the 100-digit seed, ensuring a high level of security for sensitive data, such as video feeds and lock information. The keys are generated without transmission, protecting against interception.
- **Secondary Group:**
Low-power sensors generate keys using the smaller 11-digit seed and the common prefix. This ensures manageable computational requirements while maintaining sufficient security for less sensitive data, such as temperature readings or motion detection.

Step 3: Inter-Group Communication

The central hub mediates communication between the two groups:

- **Sensors (Secondary Group):** Encrypt data with autonomously generated keys using reduced parameters. The hub decrypts and, if needed, retransmits the data to the Primary Group.
- **Primary Group Devices:** Communicate directly using robust keys generated with complex parameters.

Example Workflow:

When the motion sensor detects movement, it sends an encrypted message to the hub. The hub decrypts the message, verifies if a response is needed, and notifies the security camera to start recording. Communication between the hub and the camera uses stronger keys from the Primary Group.

Step 4: Key Regeneration

- **Primary Group:**
Devices periodically regenerate keys using the common prefix of previously generated primes as the new seed. This keeps keys updated and reduces compromise risks.
- **Secondary Group:**
Sensors also regenerate keys using their common prefix as the new seed, though at a lower frequency, as the transmitted data is less critical.

Benefits:

- **Flexibility:** Different parameters for groups allow devices with varying computational capacities to participate in the same network without compromising overall security.

- **Energy Efficiency:** Low-power sensors avoid complex computations, reducing energy use and extending battery life.
- **Scalable Security:** High-security levels are maintained for critical devices, while less critical devices are still adequately protected.

Additional Security Measures

To further enhance security, MAX can rotate algorithms for prime number generation. For example, different algorithms may be used to find primes with varying digit lengths or specific properties. This approach complicates prediction or compromise of key generation, ensuring robustness against attacks.

In these use cases, MAX demonstrates its scalability and adaptability to devices with different capabilities. By enabling autonomous key generation without transmission, MAX significantly improves IoT security compared to traditional approaches. Its ability to function without a central network and adapt to resource constraints makes it an ideal solution for securing distributed and potentially vulnerable IoT environments.

CHAPTER 5:

VULNERABILITY MANAGEMENT AND ADVANCED SECURITY SOLUTIONS

MAX represents an innovative approach to cryptographic key management in the Internet of Things (IoT). However, like any cryptographic system, it is essential to consider potential vulnerabilities and implement solutions to effectively address these risks. This section explores some of the key challenges associated with implementing MAX and solutions to enhance its robustness and security, thereby improving the overall security of IoT systems.

1. Device Compromise

A common scenario in cryptographic systems is the physical compromise of a device, for instance, if an attacker gains physical access to the device and extracts the initial seed or other critical information. In this context, MAX, like traditional cryptographic systems, is not immune to this risk.

Solution:

To mitigate this risk, MAX can be integrated with **Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs)**, such as Intel SGX, which create a secure and isolated area within the device. This environment protects the initial seed and other critical parameters, reducing the likelihood of an attacker extracting this information even with physical access to the device.

2. Device Synchronization

Devices must be accurately synchronized to ensure they use the same seed and iteration number at the same time for key generation. Synchronization among distributed devices is a key challenge for implementing MAX in IoT.

Solution:

- **Time Synchronization Protocols:** Use protocols such as **Network Time Protocol (NTP)** or **Precision Time Protocol (PTP)** to synchronize device clocks accurately.
- **Consistency Verification Mechanism:** Implement a mechanism to detect if a device has lost synchronization and trigger a new synchronization phase to realign the parameters.

Note: Precise synchronization and compromised device management are common challenges in distributed environments like IoT. While potential solutions have been explored, contributions from cryptography experts are welcome to develop optimal strategies for synchronization and compromise detection, ensuring the system's robustness.

3. System Compromise and Reset

If a device is compromised and an attacker accesses the initial seed or iteration number, the entire system could be at risk. Addressing this vulnerability requires a rapid recovery mechanism.

Solution:

- **Automatic Reset Mechanism:** If the system detects an anomaly, such as a compromised device or a potential breach, it can automatically re-synchronize all devices by securely distributing new initial parameters (seed and iterations).
- **Secure Channels or TEEs:** Use secure channels or Trusted Execution Environments to ensure the safe distribution of new parameters without interception.

4. Continuous Key Regeneration

One of MAX's most powerful features is its ability to autonomously generate and periodically regenerate cryptographic keys. This makes the system more secure than traditional algorithms that rely on static keys, reducing the chance for attackers to compromise a key and exploit it long-term.

Solution:

- **Periodic Key Regeneration:** Keys are regenerated at regular intervals using the common prefix of previously generated prime numbers as the new seed. This ensures keys remain fresh and limits an attacker's ability to exploit a compromised key for extended periods.
- **No Key Transmission:** The periodic regeneration occurs without transmitting new keys, eliminating vulnerabilities associated with key transmission.

5. Adaptation to Heterogeneous Devices

The IoT ecosystem comprises devices with vastly different computational capabilities. Some devices, like temperature or motion sensors, have very limited computational power and cannot handle large prime numbers or high iteration counts.

Solution:

- **Scalable Parameters:** MAX supports the creation of a parallel system within the IoT network that uses lighter parameters while maintaining adequate security levels.

Key Advantages of MAX

MAX addresses many vulnerabilities that affect traditional cryptographic systems, significantly reducing the risk of compromise by eliminating the need for key transmission. The challenges of synchronization, device compromise, and key regeneration are managed through the integration of advanced technologies, including:

- **Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs)**

- **Accurate Synchronization Protocols**
- **Automatic Reset Mechanisms**

MAX aims to provide a more secure and modern cryptographic solution, adaptable to a heterogeneous and distributed IoT context, offering a superior level of security compared to traditional approaches. By addressing critical vulnerabilities and leveraging advanced technologies, MAX ensures robust protection for IoT systems, even in challenging and resource-constrained environments.

CHAPTER 6:

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The application of the MAX algorithm in IoT represents a promising solution for enhancing the security of distributed networks through its ability to autonomously and securely generate cryptographic keys. By eliminating the need for key transmission between devices, MAX significantly reduces the attack surface and provides greater protection against vulnerabilities inherent in traditional cryptographic systems.

The introduction of a parallel system with lighter security parameters is a crucial step in adapting MAX to the varied computational capacities of IoT devices. This approach allows low-power devices to participate in the network without compromising overall security by using lighter parameters, such as smaller prime numbers and fewer iterations. Meanwhile, the main system ensures maximum security for critical devices, while the parallel system offers adequate protection for resource-constrained devices.

Future Developments

1. Testing in Real Environments

- Conduct extensive testing of the MAX algorithm in real IoT environments to evaluate its effectiveness and scalability on a large scale.
- Validation of the parallel system is particularly crucial to ensure that low-power devices can securely and efficiently generate and use cryptographic keys.

2. Integration with Blockchain Technologies

- Integrate MAX with blockchain to enhance system security, enabling the secure distribution of the initial seed and synchronization parameters.
- This approach ensures greater resilience during the initialization phase, further reducing the risk of compromise.

3. Development of Detection and Reset Mechanisms

- An essential aspect of system security is the ability to detect device compromises and perform automatic resets.
- If a device is compromised, the system should generate new initial parameters and securely re-synchronize all devices, ensuring a rapid response and minimizing the impact of the attack.

4. Optimization for Low-Power Devices

- Conduct further research to optimize MAX for low-power devices by reducing the number of iterations or using smaller prime numbers while maintaining adequate security levels.
- The goal is to make MAX accessible to the most constrained devices, improving computational efficiency without compromising protection.

5. **Extension to Multi-Network Contexts**

- Extend MAX to support multi-network contexts, where different IoT networks with varying security levels and parameters can communicate securely.
- This interoperability is essential for complex environments, such as industrial settings or smart cities, where security must be guaranteed across subsystems with diverse resources.

The MAX algorithm offers an innovative and scalable solution to address IoT security challenges, providing autonomous and secure key management without the need for key transmission. Future efforts will focus on field testing, integration with emerging technologies, and optimization to further enhance the system's security and efficiency, making it adaptable to a wide range of devices and scenarios.

Additional Details:

- Full experimental results and performance data for the MAX algorithm are available in the published version on **Zenodo**.
- The document includes detailed tests demonstrating MAX's ability to rapidly generate prime numbers, even with high iteration counts.

Hardware Testing:

- To date, the algorithm has been tested on high-performance hardware, such as a MacBook Pro.
- The next logical step is to extend testing to resource-limited IoT devices, such as microcontrollers (e.g., Raspberry Pi or ESP32), to assess performance in constrained environments and simulate real-world operational contexts.

Collaboration and Validation:

Practical validation of MAX requires engagement with experts and industry partners. Future steps include collaboration with organizations capable of supporting large-scale testing in real-world environments, contributing to the further development of MAX and validating its effectiveness in operational conditions.

Sincerely,

Massimo Russo

Varese, November 16, 2024